

Investigating Novel Etiologies of Skin Cancer. The Correlation Between Nitrosamines in Pharmaceuticals and Photocarcinogenesis: The ROS-Nitric Oxide Interplay/Procarcinogenic Action (During Polymedication Intake) as Skin Cancer Triggering Factor

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Abstract

The surrounding environment is a risk zone that could disrupt tissue homeostasis or tissue integrity, which could have frequent and fatal consequences for the affected organisms. Nitrosamines, as already known photocarcinogens in medicines, are among the substances that, in one form or another, enter the human body and could trigger a cascade of processes leading to probable mutations and skin cancer development and progression. The elimination of these cutaneous tumors is a serious challenge for dermatologic surgeons.

We present a case of a primary defect in the right nasal ala, following basal cell carcinoma excision, successfully reconstructed both functionally and aesthetically using dermatologic surgery procedure.

The article comments mainly on the possible pathogenetic role of the systemic medication taken by the patient to date, consisting of amlodipine, valsartan, bisoprolol, timolol, clopidogrel, pantoprazole, rosuvastatin, and latanoprost, in relation to the concepts of phototoxicity and photo carcinogenicity.

Nitrosamines, as known contaminants in those drugs, are known to be photolabile and, under the influence of solar radiation, undergo photodecomposition and generate nitric oxide. The last one interacts with ROS and regarding the current scientific knowledge is/ could be associated with the subsequent generation of mutations responsible for skin cancer. Drug related Nitroso-Photo Carcinogenesis seems to be an important part of the skin cancers pathogenesis.

For this reason, the intake of polymedication, potentially contaminated with nitrosamines or prone to forming them in an acidic/gastric environment, could be considered as extremely problematic in terms of skin cancer generation.

More Information

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At the same time, it should not be overlooked that many types of severe and risky dermatosurgical procedures performed in our patient, but not only, could be probably avoided entirely, given that the cause of skin cancer could be mediated precisely through the exposure of the human organism to known photo-carcinogens or so-called nitrosamines: pro carcinogenic substances also distributed through medicines.

Introduction

Contamination of the body with certain nitrosamines could be triggered by two mechanisms: 1) Exogenously, during the synthesis of a certain drug outside the body, as is the case with valsartan, for example/exogenous Nitrosogenesis of skin cancer [1] or 2) based on endogenous occurrence/endogenous Nitrosogenesis of skin cancer: when certain medications contain free secondary or tertiary amino groups, which in the stomach (under acidic conditions) and in the presence of nitrite-rich food form nitrosamines [2,3].

In practice, the patient we described initially took several medications that, according to scientific literature, are associated with: 1) the potential presence of finished nitrosamines in the medication (such as valsartan, for example), but also 2) the formation of endogenous nitrosamines in the context of taking amlodipine/bisoprolol, rosuvastatin, clopidogrel and timolol, which contain secondary/tertiary amino groups, and could therefore subsequently generate or mediate photo-carcinogenicity.

In this context we would like to analyse and comment the possible relation of nitrosamines in drugs to the generation of photo-carcinogenicity via photodecomposition of the nitrosamine under UV light (before its metabolization in the liver) as a substantial cofactor for the development and progression of skin cancer.

Case Report

A 79-year-old female presented to the dermatology department with primary complaint of a bleeding tumor formation located in the right nostril, present for 6-7 months.

Her medical history included hysterectomy in 2015, acute left-sided heart failure, hypertensive crisis, grade 3 hypertension, mild to moderate mitral regurgitation, mild to moderate tricuspid regurgitation, previous ischemic stroke, combined oto-neurological syndrome, hiatal hernia, reflux esophagitis, antral erythematous gastritis, dyslipidemia, and biliary reflux. She has been on systemic therapy with amlodipine /valsartan 5mg/160mg (half a tablet daily for 4 months), bisoprolol fumarate 5 mg (half a tablet twice daily for 5 years), clopidogrel 75 mg (once daily for 3 years, discontinued 20 days prior to hospitalization), latanoprost 50 microgram/ml eye drops(once daily for 1 year), dorzolamide/timolol 2 %/0.5 % eye drops (twice daily for 1 year), pantoprazole 40 mg (once in the morning for 15 years), and rosuvastatin 10 mg (once in the evening for 2 months).

Dermatological examination revealed a rounded, reddish, bleeding tumor-like lesion with a central crust, measuring 0.5 cm in diameter, located on the right nasal ala and clinically suspicious for basal cell carcinoma (Fig.1).

Figure 1: A Small Tumour Like Lesion in the Area of Ala Nasi Suspicious for Basal Cell Carcinoma

Figure 2: Severe Adverse Drug Events Due to the Possible Intake of Phototoxic Drugs. Immediate Postoperative Image after BCC Removal. Reconstruction of the Primary Defect using a Shark Flap

The lesion was preoperatively marked followed by surgical removal of the lesion using a circular excision under 2% lidocaine local anesthesia. Reconstruction of the primary wound defect was performed a shark flap (Fig.2).

Figure 3: Postoperative Image after 1 Month

Discussion

Based on the possible influence of nitrosamines as potential/ real photocarcinogens [4-6], we would like to highlight several key aspects of taking medication that tend to form nitrosamines in the body but also contain ready-made nitrosamines that arise in the medication itself before it is taken (NDMA in valsartan for example) [1].

The content of secondary or tertiary amino groups could prove to be a risk factor for patients, especially regarding skin cancer, for example.

Recently published scientific data are extremely encouraging in this regard, as they confirm: 1) the presence of a second nitrosamine after nitrosomorpholine, namely nitrosoproline, which is phototoxic/photocarcinogenic, genotoxic before metabolic activation and after exposure to UVA radiation, 2) its mutagenicity manifests itself in laboratory conditions in human-derived keratinocytes, 3) its genotoxic effect is dose-dependent, and 4) at the same time, NO (nitric oxide), a known procarcinogenic mediator, is released [4].

Histopathological examination confirmed invasive basal cell carcinoma, staged as T1NxMxR1. Regular follow-up visits were scheduled (Fig.3,4), with re-excision recommended if necessary.

Figure 4: Postoperative Image after 2 Months

Bisoprolol, a beta-blocker, contains a secondary amine functional group [7,8].

Timolol is also a beta-adrenergic receptor blocker (beta-blocker) that contains a secondary amino group in its molecular structure [9].

This group is part of the isopropylamine side chain, specifically a tert-butylamino group, which is attached to the thiadiazole ring via an oxygen bridge.

The secondary amine, along with the other structural features, contributes to timolol's ability to bind and block beta-adrenergic receptors, leading to its effects as a beta-blocker [9].

It is precisely this variable model of Photo-Nitroso Carcinogenesis that could explain the issues surrounding the degree of phototoxicity of a given drug: it is multifactorial and extremely variable, as it also depends on:

- 1) the acidic environment,
- 2) a diet rich in nitrites,
- 3) the presence of certain secondary or tertiary amino groups in the drug,
- or 4) the already exogenously ready-made/ created, synthesized nitrosamine.

A similar argument could be made regarding the additional/parallel intake of clopidogrel by the patient

presented in the publication: Clopidogrel, an antiplatelet drug, contains a tertiary amino group [10,11]. This group is part of the thienopyridine structure, specifically a 4,5,6,7-tetrahydrothieno[3,2-c]pyridine [10,11].

Although there is practically no data on the Photo carcinogenicity of clopidogrel in the medical literature, the drug could indirectly participate in such processes: The presence of a tertiary amino group in its structure could potentially promote the generation of nitrosamines in the stomach, which could subsequently generate probable Photo Nitroso Carcinogenicity: in the context of photodecomposition of nitrosamines and release of nitric oxide, for example (after their resorption and exposure to ultraviolet radiation) [12,13].

Rosuvastatin, a cholesterol-lowering medication, can cause phototoxicity, meaning it can make your skin more sensitive to sunlight and UV radiation [14].

The drug exists in the form of Nitroso-rosuvastatin [15], which suggests that under the influence of ultraviolet light, it could also be photocarcinogenic (after absorption and deposition in the skin, for example/before its metabolisation) to humans [16,17]. The situation is similar with the intake of nitroso pantoprazole in this case [18].

Pantoprazole, a proton pump inhibitor (PPI), can cause photosensitivity, a condition where the skin becomes overly sensitive to sunlight. This can manifest as drug-induced photosensitivity, which may include phototoxic reactions (resembling sunburn) or drug-induced lupus erythematosus (DILE) [19].

The amlodipine taken by our patient is known to cause photosensitivity in general [20,21], but also to be listed by the FDA as a drug potentially contaminated with nitrosamines, which have a certain carcinogenic potential: 5 for N-nitroso amlodipine [22].

In the case of nitrite-rich foods, this would promote the formation of nitrosamines in the stomach, their subsequent resorption, photodecomposition after deposition in the skin and exposure to ultraviolet radiation, as well as the subsequent development of keratinocyte skin cancer: the clinical-pathological correlations in this regard are more than indicative, especially in the context of polymedication [5,23-25].

The patient described took several drugs that are associated with the potential to generate nitrosamines endogenously (under acidic conditions and in the presence of nitrite-rich food) or to be exogenously contaminated with nitrosamines, such as valsartan, for example. Likely, this type of reaction could also be considered nitroso-induced and photo-mediated, skin cancer provoking one.

Valsartan is a drug that may contain several or up to several different nitrosamines, which arise even before the tablet is taken by patients [26].

Because these are known carcinogens/ photocarcinogens [4-6], the risk of subsequent development of skin cancer should be considered serious or significant [27].

This seriousness applies to both keratinocyte cancers and melanomas [1,28-30].

It is precisely this lack of selectivity (development of keratinocyte and melanocyte skin cancer) that could be defined as evidence of the photo-toxicity/ photo carcinogenicity (in general) of nitrosamines in medicinal products.

There is also no shortage of confirmatory clinical-pathological correlations on the subject of valsartan and the development of keratinocyte cancer on the background of problematic polymedication [23,27].

The last ones (nitrosamines) turn out to be photolabile after potential resorption and deposition in the skin, and under the influence of solar radiation (photodecomposition) could be linked to the release of one of the strongest (concentration/situation-dependent) procarcinogenic mediators involved in the pathogenesis of skin cancer (but not only): nitric oxide (NO) [31].

Nitric oxide (NO) plays a complex and often contradictory role in skin cancer development [31,32]. It can surely contribute to UV-induced DNA damage and suppresses the immune system, both of which are factors in skin cancer development and progression [33].

Nitric oxide interacts with ROS, and in a number of publications, it is precisely this interaction that could lead to the generation of mutagenic, carcinogenic effects and the subsequent development of skin cancer (melanoma), as well as breast and colon cancer [34-36]. Specifically the role of Nitric oxide / NO in BCC is not as well-defined as in other cancers, but it's known to influence the tumor microenvironment and potentially affect cancer cell behavior.

However, if, in the context of multidrug therapy, nitrosamines are considered as donors of nitric oxide, formed after photodecomposition upon exposure to solar radiation (after resorption in the body), the clinical-pathological correlations in this direction remain more than indicative of their pro carcinogenic role [5,16,17,23-25,27-30].

The latanoprost taken by the patient could also prove problematic: Although not a direct phototoxic effect, latanoprost can increase sensitivity to light, potentially making eyes more susceptible to discomfort or damage from bright light [37].

The drug latanoprost is in fact a direct generator of nitric oxide [37], which under certain conditions could be associated with the generation of skin cancer when interacting with ROS and under the influence of sunlight.

The problem with the permanent intake of nitrosamines in their finished form or their generation in the gastrointestinal tract remains multifactorial and difficult to recognize for clinicians and researchers.

The same applies to the metabolism of nitrosamines. According to scientific data, this metabolism could take place both in the liver and in the gut microbiota [30].

Growing amount of evidence indicates that the human microbiota plays a key role in both the initiation and progression of some types of cancer [38]. The gut microbiota plays a role in metabolizing these nitrosamines.

Specific bacteria can also either activate or detoxify nitrosamines, which in turn can affect the risk and severity of nitrosamine-induced cancers [38,39].

From an analytical point of view, the metabolism of nitrosamines gives rise to the following considerations: NDMA, found in valsartan, ranitidine and several other medications, for example, is directly carcinogenic before it is metabolized in the liver, mediated by the direct activation of RAS oncogenes [40]. Its metabolized, methylated form, also known as methylidiazonium, is also mutagenic [40].

In practice, we have a probable bi-carcinogen [40], which is also photolabile and subject to photodecomposition [4,6,41].

In the context of potential photodecomposition in the skin area and before metabolism in the liver (after resorption when taking certain contaminated medicinal products, for example: seven drugs in the patient we described within the paper), one of the well-known procarcinogenic mediators in the body is released: nitric oxide [6], a potent procarcinogenic mediator involved in the skin cancer pathogenesis [5,34-36].

In practice, a nitrosamine could prove to be a triple carcinogen with different modes of action: before and after metabolism [40], but also through photodecomposition in the skin area, for example [4-6].

Conclusions

The polycarcinogenic nature of each nitrosamine (exogenously produced and subsequently introduced into the body) or nitroso compound on the background of polymedication intake of products containing secondary or tertiary amino groups (generated endogenously nitrosamines) proves to be problematic. It is also problematic due to the generation of photocarcinogenicity after photodecomposition and the subsequent development of various forms of skin cancer.

Future efforts by regulators should be directed towards the permanent and effective elimination of nitroso compounds in medicinal products and finding alternative solutions to the immediate shortages resulting from this.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Ethics approval statement is not required.

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